

DROWSINESS DETECTION SYSTEM USING EYE ASPECT RATIO TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Transportation is widely used to allow user travel conveniently from place to place, for a personal or official purpose. Travel during peak hour or holiday, expose the driver to traffic jam for several hours, thus cause the driver to feel drowsy easily due to high concentration and lack of rest. This situation contributes to the increasing of the percentage of car accidents due to car driver fatigue is the primary origin of the car accident. In this paper, an image detection drowsiness system is proposed to detect the state of the car driver using Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) technique. A developed system that occupied with the Pi camera, Raspberry Pi 4 and GPS module are used to detect and analyse continuously the state of eye closure in real time. This system is able to recognize whether the driver is drowsy or not, with the initial, wearing spectacles, dim light and microsleep condition. Experimental conducted successfully give 90% of accuracy. This situation can increase the vigilance of drivers significantly.

INTRODUCTION

Transportation is a great invention that allows human beings to explore the other places for a long-range distance. In this contemporary era, traffic is a basic need for every human

being and the number of transportations on the road is increasing obviously year by year. This situation causes a traffic jam which leads to the time of travel become longer. This may cause the driver feel drowsiness during the long term of traveling time. Nowadays, statistics show that road accidents are the primary origin of the number of people death, compare to other roots causes all over the world. There are a lot of sources to lead road accidents, the situation of the road such as slippery and pot hole, the condition of the vehicle, the braking system problem and the main problem is the attitude of the driver. The attitude of the driver that may contribute the drowsiness effect due to the driver does not have enough rest thus may cause the road accident. Each human being has the limit including the duration of the driving. Therefore, driver drives should be controlling in a standard period to avoid excessive fatigue and tiredness. Tiredness leads the driver to feel sleepy and loss of focus on the road. What is drowsiness? Drowsiness is a complex phenomenon that states a decrease in alerts and conscious levels of the driver. Different technologies are developed to overcome this problem due to no direct mechanism to detect and measure the drowsiness. One of the technologies is based on the vehicle like autonomous driving that can monitor steering wheel direction,

keep the car in lane position and pressure on the accelerator continuous controlling by the engine control unit (ECU), however this is not the most accurate solution for this problem. On the other hands, the physiological of the driver, which continuously measure the driver heart rate and brain activity by electrocardiogram (ECG), electroencephalogram (EEG), electrooculogram (EOG) and electromyogram (EMG) using a particular custom device was invested, up till now it is an impracticable solution [2]. Another technology is based on the behaviour of the driver, which is tracked the blinking frequency of eye closure using a camera continuously in real-time. This is considered the best and ideal solution to overcome the drowsiness of a driver [3]. Nowadays, some car is occupied with accessories that able to track and analysed the eye closure, once the system detecting the eye, the number of eye closure is analysed. Thus, comparison data with the specified algorithm is performed to identify the eye condition. The driver is alerted through an alarm for any positive drowsy condition. The drowsiness can be identified through some natural action such as blinking of eyes, yawning, eye closure and head pose [4]. This can be done by installing a camera in front of the driver to capture the real time images of the driver [5]. The driver's images are then further processed to detect the drowsiness of the driver. This can be done by performing live monitoring of Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) by application of image processing. The real time images are processed using pre-trained Neural Network based Dlib functions. In landmarks retuned Dlib predictor function, each eye is represented by 6 (x, y) coordinates starting at the left-corner of the eye and working

clockwise around the remainder of the region.

LITERATURE SURVEY

K. Kaida, M. Takahashi, T. Åkerstedt, A. Nakata, Y. Otsuka, T. Haratani, and K. Fukasawa, "Validation of the karolinska sleepiness scale against performance and EEG variables," *Clinical Neurophysiology*, vol. 117, no. 7, 2006.

The Karolinska sleepiness scale (KSS) is frequently used for evaluating subjective sleepiness. The main aim of the present study was to investigate the validity and reliability of the KSS with electroencephalographic, behavioral and other subjective indicators of sleepiness. Sleepiness is involved in a large part of the accidents in transportation and in other areas of industry (Maycock, 1996). Subjective reports are a convenient way of gathering information about sleepiness in field and laboratory studies. For reports of habitual sleepiness, the Epworth sleepiness scale (Johns, 1991) is frequently used. For reports of instantaneous sleepiness (across the day and night), visual analogue scales (Monk, 1989) or Likert scales, like the 7-graded Stanford sleepiness scale (Hoddes et al., 1973) or the 9-graded Karolinska sleepiness scale (KSS) (Åkerstedt and Gillberg, 1990), are often used. The KSS was originally developed to constitute a one-dimensional scale of sleepiness and was validated against alpha and theta electroencephalographic (EEG) activity as well as slow eye movement electrooculographic (EOG) activity (Åkerstedt and Gillberg, 1990). It has been widely used and provided reasonable results in studies of shift work (Axelsson et al., 2004, Gillberg, 1998, Härmä et al., 2002, Ingre et al., 2004, Sallinen et al., 2004, Sallinen et al., 2005), jet lag (Suhner et al., 1998), driving abilities (Åkerstedt et al., 2005, Belz et al., 2004, Horne and Balk, 2004, Kecklund and

Åkerstedt, 1993, Otmani et al., 2005, Philip et al., 2005, Reyner and Horne, 1998), attention and performance (Gillberg et al., 1994, Gillberg et al., 1996, Kräuchi et al., 2004, Reyner and Horne, 1998) and clinical settings (Schwartz, 2005, Söderström et al., 2004).

K. Arai, and R. Mardiyanto, “Real time blinking detection based on Gabor filter,” International Journal of Recent Trends in Human Computer Interaction (IJHCI), vol. 1, no. 3, 2010, pp. 33-45.

New method of blinking detection is proposed. The utmost important of blinking detection method is robust against different users, noise, and also change of eye shape. In this paper, we propose blinking detection method by measuring the distance between two arcs of eye (upper part and lower part). We detect eye arcs by apply Gabor filter onto eye image. As we know that Gabor filter has advantage on image processing application since it able to extract spatial localized spectral features such as line, arch, and other shapes. After two of eye arcs are detected, we measure the distance between arcs of eye by using connected labeling method. The open eye is marked by the distance between two arcs is more than threshold and otherwise, the closed eye is marked by the distance less than threshold. The experiment result shows that our proposed method robust enough against different users, noise, and eye shape changes with perfectly accuracy. Blinking as one of eye movement activity beside glance has been used to keep the moisture of eye. Blinking helps eye to spread the tears and also remove unwanted things from eye.

R. O. Mbouna, S. G. Kong, and M. G. Chun, “Visual Analysis of Eye State and Head Pose for Driver Alertness Monitoring” IEEE Transaction on Intelligent Transportation Systems, vol. 14, no. 3. 2013.

In this study we demonstrate a novel Brain Computer Interface (BCI) approach to detect driver distraction events to improve road safety. We use a commercial wireless headset that generates EEG signals from the brain. We collected real EEG signals from participants who undertook a 40-minute driving simulation and were required to perform different tasks while driving. These signals are segmented into short windows and labelled using a time series classification (TSC) model. We studied different TSC approaches and designed a Long term Recurrent Convolutional Network (LCRN) model for this task. Our results showed that our LRCN model performs better than the state of the art TSC models at detecting driver distraction events Every year, nearly 1.25 million people die from car accidents. On average 3,287 die every day and the numbers are still rising. According to two news sources, distracted driving is the major cause of car accidents for the past decades. Drivers are now more easily distracted than ever and frequently stop paying attention to the road in response to mobile devices, navigation systems and complex control systems. It is predicted that road traffic injuries will become the fifth leading cause of death by 2030 if no actions are taken. Therefore, it is important to detect driver distraction events. Various video (eye tracking) and speech processing approaches have been proposed to detect driver distraction .These approaches are sometimes infeasible. For example, video processing approaches are less effective with insufficient lighting especially at night when the driver has a higher chance of being less focused on the road. In car racing environments, drivers are required to wear fire protective suits and helmets that cover their faces, making video processing methods ineffective. High levels of background noise during driving, for example sound from the engine, radio or wind noise, may sound processing approaches.

Dasgupta, A. George, S. L. Happy, and A. Routray “A Vision-Based System for Monitoring the Loss of Attention in Automotive Drivers” *IEEE Transaction on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2013.

On-board monitoring of the alertness level of an automotive driver has been a challenging research in transportation safety and management. In this paper, we propose a robust real-time embedded platform to monitor the loss of attention of the driver during day as well as night driving conditions. The PERcentage of eye CLOSure (PERCLOS) has been used as the indicator of the alertness level. In this approach, the face is detected using Haar-like features and tracked using a Kalman Filter. The Eyes are detected using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) during day time and the block Local Binary Pattern (LBP) features during night. Finally the eye state is classified as open or closed using Support Vector Machines (SVM). In-plane and off-plane rotations of the driver’s face have been compensated using Affine and Perspective Transformation respectively. Compensation in illumination variation is carried out using Bi-Histogram Equalization (BHE). The algorithm has been cross-validated using brain signals and finally been implemented on a Single Board Computer (SBC) having Intel Atom processor, 1 GB RAM, 1.66 GHz clock, x86 architecture, Windows Embedded XP operating system. The system is found to be robust under actual driving conditions. Several approaches have been reported to develop systems for on-board monitoring of the alertness level in automotive drivers. The work in [23] reports a system named as Driver AssIsting SYstem (DAISY) as a monitoring and warning aid for the driver in longitudinal and lateral control on German motorways. The warnings are

generated based on the knowledge of the behavioural state and condition of the driver.

S. Tereza, and J. Cech, "Eye Blink Detection Using Facial Landmarks." *21st Computer Vision Winter Workshop, Rimske Toplice, Slovenia*. 2016.

A real-time algorithm to detect eye blinks in a video sequence from a standard camera is proposed. Recent landmark detectors, trained on in-the-wild datasets exhibit excellent robustness against a head orientation with respect to a camera, varying illumination and facial expressions. We show that the landmarks are detected precisely enough to reliably estimate the level of the eye opening. The proposed algorithm therefore estimates the landmark positions, extracts a single scalar quantity – eye aspect ratio (EAR) – characterizing the eye opening in each frame. Finally, an SVM classifier detects eye blinks as a pattern of EAR values in a short temporal window. The simple algorithm outperforms the state-of-the-art results on two standard datasets. Detecting eye blinks is important for instance in systems that monitor a human operator vigilance, e.g. driver drowsiness [5, 13], in systems that warn a computer user staring at the screen without blinking for a long time to prevent the dry eye and the computer vision syndromes, in human-computer interfaces that ease communication for disabled people, or for anti-spoofing protection in face recognition systems. Existing methods are either active or passive. Active methods are reliable but use special hardware, often expensive and intrusive, e.g. infrared cameras and illuminators, wearable devices, glasses with a special close-up camera observing the eyes. While the passive systems rely on a standard remote camera only. Many methods have been proposed to automatically detect eye blinks in a video sequence. Several methods are based on a motion estimation in the eye

region. Typically, the face and eyes are detected by a Viola-Jones type detector.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

ARUDINO:

The Arduino is a family of microcontroller boards to simplify electronic design, prototyping and experimenting for artists, hackers, hobbyists, but also many professionals. People use it as brains for their robots, to build new digital music instruments, or to build a system that lets your house plants tweet you when they're dry. Arduinos (we use the standard Arduino Uno) are built around an ATmega microcontroller — essentially a complete computer with CPU, RAM, Flash memory, and input/output pins, all on a single chip. Unlike, say, a Raspberry Pi, it's designed to attach all kinds of sensors, LEDs, small motors and speakers, servos, etc. directly to these pins, which can read in or output digital

or analog voltages between 0 and 5 volts. The Arduino connects to your computer via USB, where you program it in a simple language (C/C++, similar to Java) from inside the free Arduino IDE by uploading your compiled code to the board. Once programmed, the Arduino can run with the USB link back to your computer, or stand-alone without it — no keyboard or screen needed, just power.

EYE BLINK SENSOR

GENERAL DESCRIPTION The eye is illuminated by an IR led, which is powered by the +5v power supply and the reflected light is recorded by an IR photo diode. This eye blink sensor is IR based; the variation across the eye will vary as per eye blink. The exact functionality depends greatly on the positioning and aiming of the emitter and detector with respect to the eye. If the eye is closed means the output is high otherwise output is low. This to know the eye is closing or opening position. This output is give to logic circuit to indicate the alarm. This can be used for project involves controlling accident due to unconscious through eye blink.

Heart beat

The front of the sensor, with the heart logo, is where you put your finger. You'll also notice a tiny circular opening through which the

Kingbright's reverse mounted green LED shines. Just beneath the circular opening is a small ambient light photo sensor – [APDS-9008](#) from Avago. This sensor is similar to the ones used in cell phones, tablets, and laptops to adjust the screen's brightness based on the ambient lighting conditions.

DHT TEMPERATURE & HUMIDITY SENSORS.

These sensors are very basic and slow, but are great for hobbyists who want to do some basic data logging. The DHT sensors are made of two parts, a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor. There is also a very basic chip inside that does some analog to digital conversion and spits out a digital signal with the temperature and humidity. The digital signal is fairly easy to read using any microcontroller. Humidity is the measure of water vapour present in the air. The level of humidity in air affects various physical, chemical and biological processes. In industrial applications, humidity can affect the business cost of the products, health and safety of the employees. So, in semiconductor industries and control system industries measurement of humidity is very important. Humidity measurement determines the amount of moisture present in the gas that can be a mixture of water vapour, nitrogen, argon or pure gas

etc... Humidity sensors are of two types based on their measurement units. They are a relative humidity sensor and Absolute humidity sensor. DHT11 is a digital temperature and humidity sensor.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic (a piezo transducer). BeStar produces Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

MOTOR:

A DC motor (Direct Current motor) is the most common type of motor. DC motors normally have just two leads, one positive and one negative. If you connect these two leads directly to a battery, the motor will

rotate. If you switch the leads, the motor will rotate in the opposite direction.

CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a drowsiness detection system based on EAR. The role of the system is to detect eyes location from images and calculate the value of EAR. In this method each eye is labelled with 6 (x, y) coordinates in landmarks returned Dlib predictor function. The labelling is starting at the left-corner of the attention, then working clockwise round the remainder of the region. Meanwhile, there's a relation between the distance of those coordinates. Thus, it derives an equation for this relation called the attention ratio and also known as Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR). According to the experimental results, it successfully detects person during drowsy condition. However, there is still space for the performance improvement. The further work will focus on detecting the distraction and yawning of the driver. Other than that, using sensors, for example, liquor sensor and pulse sensor to distinguish liquor and heartbeat pace of the driver can be included for improvement in physiological-measure analysis.

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